

THE INTERRELATION OF STYLISTIC DEVICES AND PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH-UZBEK TRANSLATION

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Abstract. This paper is devoted to stylistic analysis of phraseological units from English into Uzbek by the examples of proverbs and idioms. The peculiarities of English idioms in its origin language, their co-relation with the stylistic devices and expressive means, linguistic and stylistic approaches of these units are included the transmission to target language, the ways and methods that can determine those peculiarities in Uzbek language. The identification of proper equivalency to the origin one, the methods of preserving semantic meaning of phraseological units' stylistic aspects into target language according to linguistic, extra-linguistic and socio-cultural approaches. The translator's attitude towards the origin source units and the translation to target language.

Keywords: phraseological units, stylistic devices, equivalency, proverbs, stylistic approaches, linguistic approaches, metaphor, metonymy, simile, repetition, hyperbole, synecdoche, literary style.

ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИХ ПРИЕМОВ И ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ В АНГЛО-УЗБЕКСКОМ ПЕРЕВОДЕ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена стилистическому анализу фразеологизмов с английского на узбекский на примерах пословиц и идиом. Особенности английских идиом в языке их происхождения, их взаимосвязь со стилистическими приемами и выразительными средствами, лингвистические и стилистические подходы этих единиц включены в передачу на язык перевода, пути и методы, которые могут определить эти особенности в узбекском языке. Определение надлежащей эквивалентности исходному тексту, методы сохранения семантического значения стилистических аспектов фразеологизмов в языке перевода в соответствии с лингвистическим, экстралингвистическим и социокультурным подходами. Отношение переводчика к единицам исходного текста и переводу на целевой язык.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, стилистические приемы, эквивалентность, пословицы, стилистические подходы, лингвистические подходы, метафора, метонимия, сравнение, повтор, гипербола, синехдох, литературный стиль.

Introduction

As a third-role player in translation of phraseological units, the translator should strive to preserve the meaning of the origin to target language units. The most important role in translation refers to linguistic, extra-linguistic and lingua-stylistic approaches of the both languages. The stylistic approach should be used commonly in translation, where the linguistic approach is obvious for both languages. The priority of impressiveness of the source units relies on stylistic devices and expressive means that contribute increasing the emotionality in the meaning. These

phraseological units can be obtained some extra-linguistic approaches, which followed by culture-specific words, stylistic units, realis or customary words. Thus, the challenge of translator is to convey the relevant phraseological elements into target language, considering the linguistic and extra-linguistic approaches. In this case, the literary translation, both significant stylistic devices in source and translated languages demand the resulted solutions. Particularly, have been chosen English-Uzbek proverbs and idioms translation examples, because they play the most important role to identify the differences, similarities and exclusively to contribute literal value of the work. From translators requires the proficiency and the skill to realize the distinction between two languages, while the translation process is widely occurred in rendering the stylistic substitutes of both languages. Indeed, the lack in translation may lead the misunderstandings between the source and target units. The point of subsequent decision of translator influences the diverse or relevant results of purpose.

Literature review

Literary translation is an art, the transmission of source literary text units to the target language deals with both interlingual approaches. The perception of semantic meaning into foreign language refers to linguistic, lexical, stylistic approaches, and how they convey into translating language, the process of preservation semantic property of original material into target language units. The literary context is guided as a complicated process to understand it is demanded an effort of translator. As G. Watson and S. Zyngier mentioned “Processing of literary text is often seen as difficult, but also worth the effort as a potentially rich and engaging source of relevant language data from which to learn” [6,p.4]. Thus, the literary context in source language has variant and complicated substitutes in target language that is vary the collaboration and at the same time involves the relevant features between two languages.

Materials and methods

Stylistics is one of the most important branches of linguistics, involves the stylistic units and approaches as in essence of literary prose. The peculiarities of stylistic units refer through the stylistic devices that occur in literary style established in word combinations by the narrator. The style in its turn can contribute the special features in the prose, creating the colorfulness, brightness and emotive essence to the utterances. Eventually, the stylistic devices and expressive means in the context intensify intentionally some structures and semantic property of a language. Most of the stylistic devices and expressive means are relevant to the phraseological units in the context or rather called the phraseologisms that modify the stylistic meaning of the word units. One may argue for conceiving the phraseological units are bounded in a root of stylistic devices or stylistic units that contributed the inclusion of phraseological units. But, as in linguistic aspect each of the cases can be studied in its own field of study, according to their semantic meaning. Thus, the phraseological units are to be learnt in a discipline of phraseology, whereby the meaning and structure play a great role to determine the usages of idioms, phraseologisms and proverbs. In this case, the phraseological units can be peculiar to any certain nations and be used in a narrow field of communication. Stylistics, as a separate branch involves the stylistic meaning of those devices and expressive means, their usages that occurred in the context relevant to the linguistic and extra-linguistic approaches of the utterance. As Paul Simpson mentioned “Stylistics is interested in language, as a function of texts in context, and it acknowledges that utterances (literary or

otherwise) are produced in a time, a place, and in a cultural and cognitive context” [5,p.3]. However, the stylistic devices and expressive means have some differentiations with the phraseological units according to their meaning and structure in the context, they have direct relationship between each other. Such kind of interrelation between phraseological units and stylistic devices can be established in parallel or simultaneous usages of both units. Those identities are found in the word constructions which refer the phraseological units that include stylistic devices. So, at this situation the cognitive and psycholinguistic approaches deliver the similarity between these units. As A. Naciscione proposed “A cognitive approach to stylistic analysis of phraseological units in discourse is a transdisciplinary search. It calls for new ways of thinking about phraseology and stylistics, and their close links with fringe disciplines, such as psycholinguistics and cognitive linguistics” [4,p.21]. As the stylistic analysis of phraseological units may identify the unity and some distinctions among these disciplines. The comparative analysis in translation can distribute the collaboration of both language units. The translational process conveys those similarity and distinctions that facilitates the concepts between two disciplines. “Phraseological units are figurative set expressions often described as “idioms”. Such units have an important role to play in human communication. They produce a considerable expressive effect for, besides conveying information, they appeal to the reader’s emotions, his aesthetic perception, his literary and cultural associations. Whenever the author of the source text uses an idiom, it is the translator’s duty to try and reproduce it with the utmost fidelity. Now an idiom’s semantics are a complex entity and there are five aspects of its meaning that will influence the translator’s choice of equivalent in the target language. They are the idiom’s figurative meaning, its literal sense, its emotive character, stylistic register and national coloring. The figurative meaning is the basic element of the idiom’s semantics” [1,p.93]. But, mainly the semantics of phraseological units rely on the relationship of words and their user. And pragmatical approaches of those idioms are can be founded in social behavior, where the set expressions are mainly reproduced through the extra-linguistic patterns. As E. Black mentioned: “Since pragmatics is the study of language in use (taking into account elements which are not covered by grammar and semantics), it is understandable that stylistics has become increasingly interested in using the insights it can offer” [2,p.2]. In this case, the main challenge lays on the translators to convey them from one language to another, preserving the semantics and structural form. But, there are some issues which translators always face to solve them, it includes the preservation of functional meanings of phraseological units or semantic meaning and forms of stylistic units. The translation theory supports preserving of phraseological meaning of units that have transmitted from source language to the target language, as determining of equivalent sufficient set expressions in a target language are derived to percept the meaning of those phraseological units to confirmative language readers. Though, the phraseologisms deal with extra-linguistic approaches of the certain and they formed according to the situation of the communication. Accordingly, stylistic devices and expressive means collaborate to convey the lexical, stylistic, linguistic and extra-linguistic approaches which built in phraseological units of source language. Indeed, the stylistic devices and expressive means of source text refer to author’s style, involves the linguistic and extra-linguistic features of utterances, though the phraseological units are obtained through the situational act of communication of nations, non-relevantly to the context, peculiar only to

source language representatives to understand them. Here, referred some examples of English-Uzbek phraseological units translation which are specific for their stylistic properties and peculiar for equivalency for equivalency method transmission.

Results and Discussions

Phraseological words in a base of stylistic units follow the equivalency methods, as a complete equivalency where the units of both languages are equal semantically and structurally, a partial equivalency refers the identity of some structures within context, that are semantically close to each other, but diverse words' usage by their lexical meaning, an absence equivalency that is completely unequal languages' units. The translator has the choice out of equivalent bounded translation methods that form according to the target language norms both linguistically and extra-linguistically.

For example:

Metaphors: Barefaced liar [3]- yuzsiz yolg'onchi,

Iron fist [3]- temir musht

Red hand [3]- qo'li qon, aybdor.

Synechdoche: All skin and bone [3]- teri suyakka borib qadalgan,

All ears [3]- butun ko'z-quloq bo'lmoq

Simile: As cold as ice [3]- muzday sovuq

Blind as a bat [3]- ko'rshapalakdek ko'rmas

Stubborn as a mule [3]- eshakday o'jar

As sly as fox [3]- tulkiday ayyor

Like fish out of water [3]- Suvdan chiqqan baliqday

Hyperbole: Head is in the clouds [3]- Boshi ko'kka yetmoq

Cat has nine lives [3]- Mushukning to'qqiz joni bor

In these mentioned examples, which phraseological units occurred in a base of stylistic devices, such as metaphor, simile, synechdoche and hyperbole. As they preserved their semantics and structure in the translation. For the complete correspondences, it is peculiar to establish the words' grammatical and lexical meaning in order to give the full version of translation. Accordingly, there are existed the complete equivalence in Uzbek language, whereby the words and sentence structure are transmitted equally to translating language. Other examples can be seen also:

Metaphor: An old flame [3]-Eski (qadrdon) do'stlar

Banana Republic [3]- kichik jinoyatlarga boy respublika

Metonymy: At death's door [3]- O'lim iskanjasida

Heaven knows [3]- Faqat Oллоhga ayon

Cry your eyes out [3]- Yig'lab yubormoq

Simile: Drink like a fish [3]- Ko'p suv ichmoq

Synechdoche: Flesh and blood [3]- Qon-qarindoshlik

The phraseological units are rendered in target language with some linguistic patterns, such as grammatical or lexical collaboration in both languages. Idioms have partial correspondences in the translating language, including the similarity of different grammatical categories and lexical units can be overviewed. Although, in partial equivalency some words are specified and adapted

to the target language, as they refer the extra-linguistical patterns of the certain nation's social and cultural uniqueness. The following examples regarded as a non-equivalency method of translation, where the translation process preserves the semantic relation and similarity between two languages, referring the extra-linguistic units in the utterances. For example:

Metaphor: Second wind [3]- Imkoniyatga ega bo'lmoq

Black hole [3]- Pullarni sovurish

Dog days [3]- Yozning issiq kunlari

Hot ticket [3]- O'ta zarur ish

Metonymy: Break the ice [3]- O'rtadagi munosabatni tiklamoq

Cut the mustard [3]- Aytilgan ishni bajarmoq

Paint the town red [3]- Ko'chani boshga ko'tarmoq

Stone dead [3]- qotib qolmoq

Hyperbole: Cloud nine [3]- Boshi ko'kka yetmoq

Blood out of stone [3]- Mashaqqatli ish, yumush

Simile: As cool as cucumber [3]- Yuragi keng inson

Repetition: Neck and neck [3]- tengma-teng bo'lmoq

First come, first served [3]- Xizmat navbat bilan

Eye for an eye [3]- yuzma-yuz

These examples include the phraseological units which do not have correspondences in target language. In order to convey their semantics, the translator uses the translating language norms, that can contribute an appropriate set expression to the origin one. The linguistic diversity between two languages may be observed, as the meaning of the phraseological units are preserved their uniqueness and similarity. For non-equivalency, during the translation the stylistic coloring may not be kept its emotional purposes, rather they might be changed to neutral collocations, in order not to lose the phraseological unity of the words. Accordingly, the phraseological units in the source language can be transformed for their correspondence in target language. The above mentioned examples co-related with phraseological units in using the expressive means and stylistic devices. In the way of conveying an exact meaning of utterances, the translator should conduct himself sufficiently as the third part of role-player between two nations during the recognizing differences. Translation of any phraseological units in a base of stylistic devices and expressive means to the foreign language should create the same emotions, impressiveness and conduction, that native language readers can involve them.

Conclusion

We tried to conduct the stylistic analysis on the examples of translation English phraseological units into Uzbek. We achieved to conclude the perception of translation of phraseological units in a base of stylistic devices and expressive means into target language through the distinction of both language units, linguistic, extra-linguistic and stylistic aspects. The main criteria the term of equivalence in translation is regarded as a specific, multi-functional approach which has been chosen in transmission of phraseologisms as complete, partial and non-equivalent methods of conveying the perception of these units into translating language. For those situations, the translator plays the most important role to convey the adequate translation recognizing interlingual differences. To conclude, it has to be mentioned that the preserving of

semantic meaning of phraseological units depend on co-relation of both interlingual communicative approaches. In any other methods, the communicative approaches should be rendered from source text to target text. The semantic structure of the phraseological units in a base of stylistic devices has to be conveyed from one language to another according to both languages' linguistic, extra-linguistic, lexical and stylistic perspectives.

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